

What ecological factors favor parthenogenesis over sexual reproduction? A study on the facultatively parthenogenetic mayfly *Alainites muticus* in natural populations

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Supplementary figure S1. Distribution of the 500 sites sampled across Switzerland for the biodiversity monitoring survey (all dots). *Alainites muticus* occurred at 214 of these sites (black dots and grey dots with a black circle). Black dots represent the 159 populations used in our study (with more than 15 *A. muticus* individuals that could be sexed, also represented in Figure 1 in the main text).

Supplementary figure S2. Partially immersed floating cage.

Supplementary figure S3. Significant negative effects of *A. muticus* densities on population sex ratios split between the first (A. n=126) and the second (B. n=125) survey. Population densities are estimated from the number of sexed individuals. The black line represents the fitted linear model and the grey shadow represents the 95% confidence interval on the fitted values. The color gradient shows the population sex ratios (proportion of females), as in Fig. 1. Note that 92 populations are common to both surveys.

Supplementary Figure S4. Significant positive effects of altitudes on community diversities split between the first (Panel **A**, n=126) and the second (Panel **B**, n=125) survey. The black line represents the fitted linear model and the grey shadow represents the 95% confidence interval on the fitted values. The color gradient shows the population sex ratios (proportion of females), as in Fig. 1. Note that 92 populations are common to both surveys.

Supplementary figure S5. Plots for the non-significant paths in Figure 2. Relationships between community diversity and population sex ratio (A), altitude and population sex ratio (B), community diversity and population density (C), and altitude and population density (D). The color gradient shows the population sex ratios (proportion of females), as in Fig. 1. Note that the 92 out of the 159 populations that were surveyed twice, both values are plotted (site ID was included as a random factor in the model).

Supplementary figure S6. Diversity peaks at mid elevation. Black color = populations used within the SEM (*i.e.*, populations with >15 sexed *A. muticus*); purple color = populations with <15 sexed *A. muticus*; gray color = populations without *A. muticus*. Triangles = 1st survey (n= 490), circles = 2nd survey (n = 474).

Supplementary figure S7. Results with **Simpson's index λ** used to quantify community diversity (instead of Shannon's index, presented in the main text). $\lambda = \sum_{i=1}^S p_i^2$, where S is richness (the total number of taxa in the dataset) and p_i the proportion of individuals belonging to the i th taxon in the dataset. **A.** Structural equation model showing expected interconnections between ecological variables and the pathways fitted to collected data. Black arrows represent significant paths with positive (solid line) or negative (dashed line) effects ($p < 0.05$). Grey arrows represent non-significant paths that were evaluated in the meta-model but removed from the final model ($p > 0.05$). Path coefficients correspond to standardized effects (strength and direction of the linear relationship between the two variables) and their probability (** when $0.001 < p < 0.01$ and *** when $p < 0.001$). R^2 values are displayed on response variables, representing the proportion of variance explained. **B.** Multivariate partial plot for the significant effect of altitude on community diversity in panel A. Note that for the 92 out of the 159 populations that were surveyed twice, both values are plotted (site ID was included as a random factor in the model). The color gradient shows the population sex ratios (proportion of females), as in Fig. 1. The black line represents the fitted linear model and the grey shadow represents the 95% confidence interval on the fitted values. Note that the positive effect of altitude on community diversity was for the altitudinal range of *A. muticus* populations. Across the full altitudinal range of all surveyed sites (including those without *A. muticus*), diversity peaks at mid elevation (see Supplementary figure S6).